

Figure 17: the vaṃśas, rajjus and sirās in the 10 by 10 vāstu for a fortress (koṭṭāṭṭālakasaṃyuta), PI 8.225-226.



 cell removed, therefore no rajju crosses it.

 sirā

 rajju

 vaṃśa